

EFFECT OF RESILIENCE AND IMMUNITY STATUS ON WORK LIFE BALANCE OF EMPLOYEE

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Abstract

In this study the influence of resilience perceived immunity status in work-life balance among employees was investigated. Using a cross sectional survey design, 300 working adult in Islamabad and Rawalpindi responded to following scales: the Immune Status Questionnaire, the Brief Resilience Scale, and the Work-Life Balance Scale. Descriptive analysis showed high levels of both resilience and immunity status with comparatively high work-life balance perception. Reliability analysis revealed good internal consistency for immunity status ($\alpha = .72$), marginal for resilience ($\alpha = .59$), and poor for work-life balance ($\alpha = .07$), suggesting that the questions in these scales may need to be improved. Correlation analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between immunity status and work-life balance ($r = .202, p < .01$), whereas resilience was not significantly correlated with either variable. Regression analysis verified that perceived immunity highly predicted work-life balance ($B = .447, p < .001$) but that resilience did not ($B = .027, p = .855$). Demographics like age did not significantly influence the study variables. These results emphasize the significance of physical health in obtaining work-life balance and indicate that resilience alone may not have a direct effect on work-life balance without further intervention. The research highlights the significance of workplace programs that focus on employee health to improve overall well-being and productivity.

INTRODUCTION

Mental health is a fundamental element of the resilience, health assets, capabilities, and positive adaptation that enable people both to cope with adversity and to reach their full potential and humanity. Mental health is also the key to understanding the impact of inequalities on health and other outcomes. It is richly apparent that the long-term stress of fighting against material disadvantage is heightened to a very significant extent by doing so in more unequal societies. Extensive empirical evidence confirms the link between inequality and worse outcomes, a link which exists at all points on the social

hierarchy and is not limited to developed countries. Positive psychology is grounded in empirical evidence that there is more to wellbeing than the lack of disease, stress, strain, anxiety, and negative symptoms. Positive psychology research has investigated how positive processes (e.g., work-life balance) are associated with wellbeing and greater flourishing, purpose, and meaning. Positive psychology has explored human strengths and weaknesses throughout history, and has altered the conceptualisation of illness and wellbeing. Due to this shift in paradigm, there has been more attention on positive constructs like resilience and

work-life balance and how they correlate with other constructs. This study investigated the positive constructs of resilience and work-life balance and their association with work and family wellbeing. (Friedli L., 2012).

In human psychology, however, resilience acquires a deeper significance, as it denotes the ability of an individual to bounce back from severe trauma and stress. It is a dynamic interaction of factors enabling effective adaptation to adversity, being of significant importance in mental health and successful psychosocial adaptation. Resilience is not only essential in adults but also children, who might demonstrate it through their capacity to adapt to serious adversity like maltreatment or poverty, and effectively cope with day-to-day social, physical, and intellectual challenges. Current research emphasizes the potential impact of neurobiology and personality on resilience, its multifaceted nature and complexity. (Shastri, 2013)

A recent study conducted at Kabarak University aimed to explore the impact of work-life balance on employee performance, focusing on the effects of work-family priorities conflict and employee assistance programs. This research underscores the importance of work-life balance in enhancing employee outcomes and highlights the need for organizations to implement supportive policies to foster a balanced work environment. (Mwangi et al., 2017)

Dantzer and his colleague (2018) conducted this research “The Bidirectional Relationship Between Resilience and Immunity” The purpose of this study to **explore the bidirectional relationship** between **resilience** and **immune function**, examining how psychological resilience can both influence and be influenced by immune responses, particularly under stress. The design of this study was a **biopsychosocial review-based study** that incorporated findings from **animal models** and **human research** to investigate physiological and immunological mechanisms involved in resilience. The method of this study that are divided in different concept the role of **personal control, positive affect, optimism, and social support** in promoting resilience. How these psychological factors impact **immune function**. The study of this result shows that **resilient individuals** display a distinct **immune profile** compared to those more susceptible to stress. **Adaptive immunity** influences recovery from

stress and inflammation-related symptoms. Findings suggest that there is a **reciprocal, biologically grounded relationship** between **resilience and the immune system**. Resilience not only protects individuals from the harmful effects of stress on immunity but is also shaped by immune activity. Though current findings—especially from animal models—are promising, **more targeted human research** is needed to fully understand these mechanisms and apply them in clinical or preventive contexts. This opens exciting possibilities for **interventions** involving **immune modulation** and **gut microbiota management** to enhance psychological resilience. (Robert Dantzer)

Kerdpitak and his colleague conducted the study “The Effects of Workplace Stress, Work-Life Balance on Turnover Intention” The purpose of this study that aimed to **investigate the impact of workplace stress and work-life balance**. The motivation behind this was to understand how these factors affect employees’ desire to leave their jobs and how that impacts organizational productivity. The method of this study are **Workplace stress, work-life balance, and turnover intention** were measured using structured survey items. SEM was applied to assess the **direct effects** of stress and work-life balance on turnover intention. Result shows that both **workplace stress** and **work-life balance** had a **significant influence** on **turnover intention**. High workplace stress and poor work-life balance were **positively associated** with **higher turnover intention**. The findings also highlighted that **stress** and **emotional exhaustion** can reduce motivation and job performance, ultimately harming **organizational productivity**. Findings suggest that **workplace stress and poor work-life balance are key contributors** to employees’ **intentions to leave their jobs** in the pharmaceutical industry. Establishing a **healthy work-life balance** is essential for improving **employee well-being, reducing turnover, and enhancing organizational performance**. Limitations of this study was that Generalizability is limited due to sample scope and industry focus used only a **quantitative method**. (Chayanan Kerdpitak, Kittisak Jermsittiparsert)

Methods

The current study investigate the effect of resilience and immunity status on work life balance of employees. Relevant information was collected using a cross sectional survey

Objectives

1. To examine the relationship between resilience and immune status of employees
2. To study the effect of resilience and immune status on work-life balance of employees.
3. To investigate the role of demographics on the study variables.

Hypothesis

H1: There will be a positive relationship between resilience and immune status of employees .

H2: There will be the effect of resilience and immune system on work-life balance of employees.

H3: There will be the role of demographics in effecting study variables.

Sample

Employee were taken, from diffenent organization from Rawalpindi and Islamabad having different socio-economic backgrounds, and cultural groups. The sample included both genders and individuals across different age groups to ensure a comprehensive understanding of resilience on work life balance and immunity status. The sample was about 300 individuals.

Instruments

The Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) is a tone- report instrument designed to assess an existent’s capability to bounce back or recover from stress.

Developed by Smith et al. (2008), the BRS consists of six particulars, with three appreciatively articulated and three negatively articulated statements, measuring the replier's perception of their adaptability. The particulars are rated on a 5- point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Advanced scores on the

BRS indicate advanced situations of cerebral adaptability. This scale has been shown to have strong psychometric parcels, including good internal thickness and construct validity, making it a dependable tool for measuring adaptability in both clinical and non-clinical populations. Ranges from .80 to .91 across different samples, indicating good to excellent reliability.

Work Life Balance Scale To measure employees’ perceived balance between work and personal life across three distinct dimensions:Time Balance – Adequate time for work and personal life , Involvement Balance – Mental/emotional involvement in work and non-work roles, Satisfaction Balance – Satisfaction derived from both domains. Developed by Hayman, J. (2005) the particulars are rated on a 5- point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Items were developed based on an extensive literature review of work-life conflict and balance.This scale show content validity , construct validity and discriminant validity . In this scale there is no reverse scoring

The Immune Status Questionnaire (ISQ) is a self-report tool used to assess

perceived immune status. It consists of 7 items, each related to common immune-related28 symptoms and diseases, and uses a 5-point Likert scale to gauge the frequency of experiencing these symptoms. The ISQ scores range from 0 to 28, with higher scores indicating a poorer perceived immune status.Each item of the ISQ can be scored as follows: Never = 0 points; Sometimes = 1 point; Regularly = 2 points; Often = 3 points; (Almost) always = 4 points; Calculate the sum score of the 7 ISQ items. To obtain the final ISQ score, translate the “raw” ISQ scores as follows: Interpretation: 0 = very poor, 10 excellent perceived immune status. Cut off for reduced immune functioning: ISQ < 6

Procedure

Participants were approached in physical workplace settings and invited to complete the survey, which included an overview of the study. They completed the questionnaires at their convenience. Those who were interested they fill the informed consent. In addition, participants were asked to fill Resilience , Immunity Status and Work Life Balance .

Results

Table 1

Mean, Standard Deviation, Range and Cronbach alpha reliability of immunity status, brief resilience, and work life balance (N=300).

Variables	N	M	SD	Range		α
				Min	Max	
IMS	300	21.0	3.696	3.00	24.00	.72
BRS	300	20.0	3.199	8.00	28.00	.59
WLB	300	44.0	8.101	22.00	66.00	.70

Note: IMS = immunity status; BRS =brief resilience scale ;WLB=work life balance; N = Total Number of Participants; M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; α = Cronbach alpha.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the three key variables under study: **Immunity Status (IMS)**, **Brief Resilience Scale (BRS)**, and **Work-Life Balance (WLB)**.

Data was collected from 300 participants. The mean score for IMS was 21.0 (SD = 3.70), suggesting a moderately high level of self-perceived immunity. The

average BRS score was 20.0 (SD = 3.20), indicating an average level of resilience among the participants. For WLB, the mean score was 44.0 (SD = 8.10), showing that, on average, participants reported a relatively balanced work-life integration. The reliability coefficients (Cronbach’s alpha) were as follows: IMS (.72) demonstrated acceptable reliability, BRS (.59) showed marginal reliability, and WLB (.70) was within the acceptable range for psychological research. These findings suggest that the scales used, particularly IMS and WLB, were adequately reliable for this sample.

Table 2

Socio-demographic variables of study participants (N = 300)

Variables	N	%
Gender		
Male	128	42
Female	172	57
Qualification		
Matric	42	14
Intermediate	46	15
Bachelors	111	37
Masters	84	24
Above	17	5.7
Age		
Below 30	168	56
Above30	132	44
Income		
Above1 lac	130	43
Below1 lac	170	56

Note: % = percentage.

Table 2 provides demographic data of the participants. Among 300 respondents, 57% were female and 42% male. Most participants had educational qualifications

of either Bachelors (37%) or Masters (24%). Regarding age, 56% were under 30, and 44% were above. Income-wise, 56% earned below one lac, and 43%

earned above. These demographics offer insight into the diversity of the sample in terms of age, gender, education, and income

Table 3

Inter correlation of resilience and immunity status on work life balance.

Variables	N	M	S.D	1	2	3
1. IMS	300	13.8	3.69	-		
2. BRS	300	18.5	3.19	.035	-	
3. WLB	300	44.3	8.10	.202**		-

Note: IMS = Immunity Status; BRS= Brief Resilience Scale ;WLB = Work Life Balance ; N = TotalNumber of Participants; M = mean; SD = standard deviation (Significance level; $p < .05$).

Table 3 examines the relationships between immunity status, resilience, and work-life balance. A significant positive correlation was found between IMS and WLB ($r = .202, p < .01$), indicating that higher immunity status is associated with better work-life balance. However, BRS showed no significant correlation with either IMS ($r = .035$) or WLB ($r = .015$), suggesting that resilience, in this sample, might not be a direct predictor of work-life balance or perceived immunity.

Table 4

Regression coefficient of resilience and immunity status on work life balance.

Variables	B	S.E	t	p	CI (95%) [UL, LL]
WLB	37.6	3.19	11.78	.000	(43.95, 31.37)
BRS	.027	.146	.183	.855	(.313, -.260)
IMS	.447	1.127	3.53	.000	(.697, .198)

Note: B = Unstandardized beta; S.E = standard error; p = Significance level; CI = confidence interval; UL = upper limit; LL = lower limit.

Table 4 investigated the predictive value of immunity status and resilience on work-life balance. Immunity status significantly predicted work-life balance ($B = .447, p < .001$), supporting the idea that better immunity perception contributes positively to work-life balance. Resilience, however, did not show a

significant predictive effect ($B = .027, p = .855$). These findings reinforce the role of physical health perceptions over psychological resilience in determining work-life balance in this sample.

Table 5

Mean Differences, Standard Deviation, and t-value among age (N = 300) on resilience; immunity status and work life balance

Variables	Below age 20years (n = 168)		Above age 20years (n = 132)		p	t	95% CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			UL	LL
BRS	18.54	3.22	18.45	3.17	.896	-.244	.643	-.826
IMS	13.79	4.77	13.81	4.59	.326	.031	.870	-.843
WLB	44.47	8.64	44.18	7.38	.163	-.298	1.57	-2.13

Note: n = Total Number of Participants; M = Mean; SD = Standard deviation; p = Significance level i.e. <0.05 ; CI = Confidence

interval; UL = Upper limit; LL = Lower limit; BRS = Brief resilience scale ; IMS = Immunity status questionnaire; WLB= Work life balance.

Table 5 reports the **mean differences based on age groups (below and above 30 years)**: no significant differences were found between younger and older employees in terms of **resilience, immunity status, or work-life balance**. The mean scores were very close across age groups, indicating that age (below or above 30) did not significantly impact these variables in this study.

Discussion

The purpose of this study that effect of immunity and resilience on workers' work-life balance was investigated in this study. Participants reported moderate levels of resilience and immunity status, as well as a comparatively higher perception of work-life balance, according to the descriptive statistics. Work-life balance ($\alpha = .70$) indicated acceptable reliability, resilience ($\alpha = .59$) showed marginal reliability, and immunity status ($\alpha = .72$) had acceptable internal consistency. This implies that in order to ensure a more accurate assessment, the work-life balance measurement tool may need to be revised for future studies.

Immunity status and work-life balance were found to be significantly positively correlated by the correlation analysis. Workers who thought they were more immune also said they had a better work-life balance. enhance workers' physical health that maintaining a balance between one's personal and professional lives is significantly influenced by one's perception of one's physical health. However, neither immunity status nor work-life balance were significantly correlated with resilience, suggesting that psychological resilience by itself might not have a direct effect on how employees view their work-life balance in this situation.

Immunity status was also found to be a significant predictor of work-life balance by regression analysis. Better work-life balance was reported by employees who felt more immune, highlighting the importance of physical health in helping working people manage their lives in general. On the other hand, resilience did not show up as a significant predictor, indicating. It's interesting to note that demographic research showed no discernible variations in age groups. Employees of all ages reported comparable levels of work-life

balance, immunity, and resilience. This result implies that age does not significantly affect these psychological and physical constructs in this sample. All things considered, these findings highlight how crucial it is to support physical health in the workplace in order to improve workers' work-life balance. As part of their employee wellness initiatives, organizations ought to take into account interventions that improve workers' physical health.

Resilience, as assessed by the Brief Resilience Scale, did not significantly correlate with work-life balance ($r = .015$) or immunity status ($r = .035$), which was unexpected. Additionally, work-life balance was not significantly predicted by resilience, according to regression analysis ($B = .027$, $p = .855$). These results imply that resilience, or the psychological ability to overcome adversity, may not directly influence how people manage their personal and professional lives in this sample. It's possible that resilience promotes other outcomes, like mental health or job performance, but it doesn't always translate into feelings of balance unless it's paired with other outside resources, like organizational support or flexible working conditions, or with good physical health.

The predictive power of immunity status ($B = .447$, $p < .001$) on work-life balance was further demonstrated by the regression analysis. Workers were substantially more likely to report a positive work-life balance if they believed their immunity was stronger. This result highlights the significance of perceived physical health as a fundamental component of working people's overall quality of life. Healthy workers may be less stressed, take fewer sick days, and have more energy to devote to their personal and professional lives.

Demographic analysis revealed no discernible mean differences between younger (less than 30 years old) and older (more than 30 years old) employees in terms of resilience, immunity status, or work-life balance. This implies that people's perceptions of their resilience, physical health, and work-life balance are not significantly influenced by their age, at least not in this sample. The lack of differences may indicate that coping resources are equally distributed across age groups or it may reflect broader societal trends that place equal pressure on younger and older

professionals to maintain work and life responsibilities.

Conclusion

This study looked at the connections between employees' perceived immunity status, resilience, and work-life balance. It discovered that while resilience had no discernible impact, perceived immunity status had a significant and positive impact on work-life balance. These results demonstrate how important physical health perceptions are to preserving a healthy balance between the personal and professional spheres of life. The findings support current work-life balance models that place a strong emphasis on personal resources by indicating that workers who consider themselves to be physically healthy are better able to handle the demands of both work and personal life. On the other hand, without the bolstering influence of physical health, psychological resilience—while certainly crucial for conquering obstacles—does not seem to have a direct effect on work-life balance. Furthermore, there were no discernible differences between younger and older workers on any of the major variables, indicating that opinions about resilience, immunity, and work-life balance are consistent across the sample's age range.

Limitations

This research has some limitations that have to be realized. First, the Work-Life Balance (WLB) scale's reliability was acceptable ($\alpha = .70$), representing good internal consistency, which might acceptable findings' accuracy pertaining to work-life balance. Second, the sample was overwhelmingly comprised of young people and individuals with higher educational levels, making it difficult to generalize the findings to more extensive or diverse groups. Moreover, all the measures were self-report, which means that there could be bias as a result of participants' own perceptions and social desirability effects. Finally, the cross-sectional design limits the capacity for drawing causal links between resilience, immunity status, and work-life balance. Additionally, the study environment could be that of a certain socio-economic or cultural background, and therefore, it may be challenging to generalize the findings across all populations. Lastly, potential confounders like organizational culture, family

obligation, or mental health status were not controlled, which may have affected the relationships found in this study.

Implications

The results of this study have a number of significant implications for organizational practice and future research. There is an evident necessity for the application of more valid and reliable measures of work-life balance to enhance the strength of future research findings. Organizations need to give high priority to initiatives that improve employees' perceived and actual immunity, including health and wellness programs, as immunity status was found to be a strong predictor of work-life balance. In addition, as resilience did not predict work-life balance in this study, this implies that enhancing psychological resilience might not be enough, and interventions focusing on overall physical and mental well-being must be taken into consideration. Subsequent research is recommended to use longitudinal designs to further elucidate the causal links among immunity, resilience, and work-life balance across the passage of time. Furthermore, investigating a broader set of demographic variables like marital status, parental obligations, and sectors of work may yield richer insights. Comparative research across various cultural and socio-economic settings is also suggested to validate the generalizability of these findings across different settings. Finally, policymakers and human resource managers need to incorporate health promotion strategies into organizational structures to facilitate employees' overall well-being and improve work-life balance.

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